

Simple and Affordable Multimedia Tools to Develop Learning Materials

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ABSTRACT

Classroom teaching can no longer depend on textbooks and whiteboard because the present condition in classrooms shows that teachers should find ways to make learning more enticing and engaging. In addition, books, pictures, and videos are not sufficient for both teachers and students because they realize that the aforementioned items are not enough to cater the ever growing demands of teachers and students. As Information Communication Technology (ICT) gradually becomes part of human life, there are calls for teachers to use ICT in developing learning materials which can elevate students' learning experience, beyond textbooks and whiteboard. ICT opens rooms for teachers to innovate with existing learning materials and provide their students with tailor-made lessons which should be more in-tune to students' needs and capabilities. There are a few ICT tools that work wonderfully simple, available in multiple platforms, and are helpful for teachers to churn innovative learning materials.

Keywords: ICT, Applications, learning materials

ABSTRAK

Pengajaran di dalam kelas tidak bisa lagi bergantung pada penggunaan buku teks dan papan tulis karena kondisi terkini di ruang kelas menunjukkan bahwa guru harus bisa menemukan cara untuk membuat pengajaran menjadi lebih menarik dan melibatkan siswa secara aktif. Selain itu, pengajaran masa kini tidak bisa lagi hanya mengandalkan buku, gambar, dan video karena baik guru dan murid menyadari hal-hal tersebut sudah tidak mencukupi lagi untuk memenuhi perkembangan tuntutan pengajaran. Karena sekarang TIK telah menjadi bagian dalam kehidupan masyarakat, kini muncul permintaan agar guru mengintegrasikan TIK ketika mengembangkan materi pelajaran yang dapat meningkatkan pengalaman belajar siswa, melampaui alam buku teks dan papan tulis. Apalagi, penggunaan TIK dalam mengembangkan materi ajar dan belajar membuka ruang bagi guru untuk berinovasi dengan materi belajar yang ada dan menyediakan pelajaran-pelajaran yang lebih sesuai dengan kebutuhan dan kemampuan siswa. Ada banyak alat-alat TIK yang mudah dipakai, tersedia dalam pelbagai platform, dan bisa menolong guru dalam membuat materi belajar yang inovatif.

Kata kunci: aplikasi, TIK, materi ajar

INTRODUCTION

The boom of internet 2.0 in mid 2000's has ushered an era of interaction and connectivity that sprawls beyond what used to be considered almost impossible. With its strong ground in inter-connection and content distribution (O'Reilly, 2005), Web 2.0, marked

by the popularity of user-generated-content websites—Friendster, Blogger, Wikipedia, FB, Twitter, provides an alternative approach to education through ICT. The websites have now offered bigger opportunities for educators to harness internet potential to extend their teaching without having to learn sophisticated programming skill. Therefore, teachers can create websites/blogs and fill them with educational content. Related to that situation, students can use the content to support their learning outside classroom. Thus, the traditional classroom interaction is enriched and transformed into blended learning, flipping classroom, and Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). This new reality of education is easily found in the success of Moodle, teaching/learning blog, YouTube classes, Coursera, and many more. Although each of those teaching learning medium has its own special feature, it has one thing in common: using audio/video as media of extended teaching (Kaufman and Mohan, 2009).

Although teaching using video/audio is not a new thing (distant learning method has pioneered this), it has become more widespread these days due to the growing success of video-sharing websites, such as, YouTube, Vimeo, and Dailymotion, and iTunes Store. Those places house hundreds of educational channels which most of them are available for free and accessible for anyone. Video and audio are regarded as a perfect companion to textbook because they convert words and sentences into a realistic learning (Harmer, 2011) and they add details that are missing in textbooks. For instance, a teacher can create a video to demonstrate a theory in a textbook with additional information that is taken from other sources (Hoffenberg and Handler, 2001). As to audio teaching, a teacher may create a recorded lecture that explains a chapter in a textbook (Harmer, 2011). Therefore, by watching the videocast or listening to audio podcast several times, students will get better comprehension than just learning from textbooks. This means students can learn a subject according to their own pace, depending on their academic ability (Dawson, 2011). In addition to that, students can learn anywhere and anytime using the powerful mobile gadgets or they can use desktop/portable computer (Jee, 2011). Furthermore, audio/videocast is potential to facilitate students with special needs--dyslectic or autistic (Burn and Reed, 1999). The benefits of this audio/video teaching approach are to allow teachers to create a rich learning material that is free from the constraints of schedule, to allow repetitive learning, to retain the same intimacy of teacher-students interaction, and to stimulate students' multiple intelligences.

One notable success story of using videocast for education is Khan Academy (Thompson, 2011). Other successful educational channel on internet is MOOC, such as, Coursera and Udemy, and podcasts library on iTunes Store. Those successes show how

strong the internet is to boost teaching and learning condition beyond the scope of classroom wall and schedule.

USING VIDEO IN CLASSROOM

Videos have been used to supplement students learning in classroom before internet age. Besides using ready made videos which are available in music/video stores, teachers occasionally have the need to use videos which are available for free on internet. The problem is that only few videos on internet can be downloaded for free and most of the videos are not downloadable. With a simple software, teachers can download videos from websites, such as, YouTube or Daily Motion, without having to spend money.

JDownloader (JD) is a download manager, similar to IDM, that can download almost anything from a website and it is free. This program is free because it is built on Java, so it does not require users to purchase it. To use this program, users only need to copy a web link (or download link) and paste it into its JD's Linkgrabber tab. When it is done, JDownloader will read the link and process it. Later, users only need to click Download button and wait until it finishes downloading the file. JD can download almost any kind of files from internet. If it is used to download a video from YouTube, it is going to read the web address and provide various types of downloadable video format (FLV, MOV, MP4, etc) in multiple resolutions (240p-720p, etc). The best thing about JD is its ability to pause a download process and resume it anytime. Although the process is halted because of power shutdown, users can resume the download process whenever the computer is on. This makes JD feels like a torrent-download software.

JDownloader is a bit impractical and too sophisticated but there is another simple way to download video using Downloadhelper (DwH) which is a small plug-in that can download video, usually, from video-hosting websites-YouTube and Vimeo. This plug-in can be downloaded directly from Firefox browser. Users just open Firefox, click Tools on toolbar, click Add-ons, and type "downloadhelper" in search box. Then, users only need to follow simple instruction and the plug-in will be installed right inside Firefox. Whenever Firefox is open, "downloadhelper" will be ready to work. If the users visit a video address on YouTube, they will see rotating red-yellow-blue balls on the right or left corner of Firefox browser. It means Downloadhelper is able to read the video file in the web address and ready to download it. Moreover, users have to choose which type of video that they want to download (MP4, FLV, High Quality, Medium Resolution, etc). Once a choice is selected, they just sit and wait until the file is completely downloaded.

It is recommended that teachers download video in MP4 since it is the most common format for video and playable by most media players. It is suggested not to download 3gp format because of its low screen resolution: making it not ideal for large screen viewing, and skipping flash-based video (FLV) due to its high energy consumption.

MAKING PODCASTS AND VIDEOCASTS

Often times, teachers are not satisfied with ready-made video and they want to make a tailor-made video which is specifically designed to meet classroom's need and students' ability. Furthermore, the podcasts/videocasts will enable students to stay up-to-date with the progress of classroom learning and both teachers and students reap benefits. Students can listen to podcasts or watch videocasts in case they have not understood the lesson in class textbook or they miss their class. On the other hand, teachers can give enriching lesson, using materials outside textbooks.

Podcasts are basically an audio record of teachers talk and the content is usually about an explanation of an academic subject. Making podcasts is quite simple because a teacher can choose to record his/her voice during actual classroom session or he/she creates a special session to record his/her teaching. If the teacher chooses the first technique, he should prepare a voice recorder (smartphone or digital voice recorder) and put it in his shirt's pocket. Then, he can record his voice in real-time while he is teaching. In terms of audio quality, voice recorder can produce acceptable audio quality but smartphone cannot produce similar result. To overcome that weak spot, a smartphone needs external microphone, such as, a plug-in mic or a lavalier mic. With lavalier microphone, the teacher only needs to attach it to the teacher's shirt, connects it to his smartphone, and does his teaching as usual. On the other side, plug-in microphone is simpler to use because he just plugs the microphone into the headphone port, puts the phone in pocket shirt (for better reception), and does his business as usual. As to software, a smartphone comes with its own pre-installed application that can record voice. If the application is not satisfying, it is possible to look for free application for voice recording in Google Store or iTunes Store. iRig Recorder or EZ Voice (free apps for iOS and Android) from IK Multimedia is very recommended for this job for those products come from a trusted brand in digital audio recording and has proved their abilities well.

If a teacher plans to make a podcast with a computer, he/she can use Audacity (freeware) and an external microphone. External microphone for computer is easy to get because any available microphone on the market or use a headphone with extension

microphone can be used. As to Audacity, one can download it for free from internet (Audacity.sourceforge.net) and install it in his computer (Windows or Mac). However, installing Audacity can be tricky because it comes in three separate packages and they all have to be installed because they are inter-related. To be safe, it is to follow the procedure described in Sourceforge's website. Once installed, Audacity can do any audio-related project, e.g., recording voice, converting audio file, modifying a record. The graphic user interface (GUI) of Audacity is quite easy to understand. It is just to click the red (record) button and to start recording his voice. When he is finished, he can click the red square button to stop recording. After that, teacher may save the recording file and convert the file into media friendly format (mp3 or aac).

While podcasts are easy to produce, as simple as recording one's voice, videocasts are more challenging because it does not only involve audio but also video. Generally, there are two kinds of videocasts; a. Video Lecture and b. Video Slideshow. A video lecture is a video of a teacher who teaches a subject in a classroom setting. The teacher may do his teaching with a whiteboard or flipchart or he delivers his lecture. For this purpose, the teacher only needs a tripod and a video recording device, such as, video camera, DSLR camera, tablet, or a smartphone. In its implementation, If the teacher needs to shoot video using smartphones/tablets, he needs to use a specialized rig, such as, JOBY Griptight, Glif, or iOgrapher (iOS Devices only). To record video, tablets and smartphones need an application to do the job. iOS users can now use the free iMovie or Camera application (Apple) to shoot and edit video, whereas Android users depend on the mercy of phone manufactures. Fortunately, there is a universal application that Android and iOS smartphone users can use, such as, YouTube Capture from Google (free). To achieve acceptable visual quality, teachers should pay attention to room lighting (Brookes in Becta) and the lens quality of the video camera. After video shooting, teachers can edit the video and distribute it online, upload into internet, or offline, making CD/DVD copies.

Video slideshow, as oppose to videocast, is a slideshow, created with slideshow software that is turned into a video. The video contains a lesson with voice narration. This kind of video is simple to produce because a teacher can produce it by using his own computer and slideshow software, such as, PowerPoint 2014. He can start his video slideshow project by, first, creating an ordinary slideshow for teaching. Upon finishing the slideshow, he adds his voice as narration to the slideshow. To do that, he just needs to click *Slideshow* on toolbar, and then chooses *Record Slideshow*. Computer screen will display the slides and the teacher starts talking as he plays the slideshow. It needs to click Exit button on

top screen and the video recording is finished. Then, the review of the slideshow can be done by playing it. If the teacher is not satisfied with the end result, he can redo the recording from the beginning. Visuals are added to make the slideshow more interesting. It will be even better if the texts/photos in the slideshow are animated with built-in animated effects in PowerPoint. To achieve visual clarity, the slideshow should take widescreen format (16:9 or 1280 x 720), use sans-serif font (Helvetica or Gill Sans), and apply 30 points font (minimum font size). To turn the slideshow in PowerPoint file into a video, the teacher only has to click File > Save as Movie > click Save. When the slideshow video is done, the teacher can, again, distribute it online (via YouTube) or offline (burning CD/DVD).

One caveat with videocast approach is the effort to produce video with good audio quality. This problem can be overcome by using an additional audio recording device. For DSLR camera, teacher can use lavalier or shotgun microphone. As to smartphones, teacher can still use lavalier microphone or direct microphone (iRig Mic Cast). If using external microphone is absolutely out-of-the-question, there is still another solution. He does the recording in an empty room and speaks loudly at built-in microphone on camera/computer (laptop).

VIDEO PROCESSING

After making videocasts, he can choose to distribute videos directly or edit them on computer for better look. Editing job is quite easy because specialized softwares are plentifully available and a few of them are free. One very simple freeware for video editing is MPEG Streamclip from Squared5.com. In mere 1.1 MB, Streamclip can convert any video into various formats. This is really useful when he needs to share the videocasts on multiple platform/gadgets. Additionally, Streamclip can even convert video into audio. Furthermore, this nifty software allows users to tweak a video in terms of resolution, size, quality, and it has watermark feature. The best part of Streamclip is the editing features that enable its users to do dirty editing such as cutting a video/audio file or joining multiple video/audio clips and it is available for Macintosh and Windows. For a video conversion, two freewares are available; Wondershare and Any Video Converter. They can work just like Streamclip but it is not necessary for users to have video editing ability.

For a more professional result, the pre-installed softwares can be good choices to refine the video produced. On Macintosh, iMovie is the best one to produce good quality video with its rich features of editing, filters, effects, and multiple platforms export. For Windows users, Windows Movie Maker (WMM), pre-installed with Windows OS, can edit

video and add effects with a fine quality. More, narration or alter the audio quality to achieve better result can be added. With iMovie or WMM, adding titles to videos will give good information to audience about the topic of the video.

Besides pre-installed softwares, there are also free softwares for video editing but they are mostly available online. YouTube, for example, gives a chance to a video uploader to edit the video online, right inside YouTube site. On the down side, online service requires a teacher to have a good internet connection. If the videocasts are created on a smartphone, teachers can edit them using the available application. On iPhone, there is iMovie for iOS which works like its sibling on desktop which is available in a simple form. As to Android, free video editing application depends on phone's manufacturer but Android users can use free app, e.g., YouTube Capture. The edited video can then be uploaded straight into YT from smartphone.

VIDEO/AUDIO RIPPING

There might be a time when teacher needs make a copy of audio or video materials, taken from a CD or DVD, for classroom usage and they want to do it with less hassle. For this need, there are four useful applications available. iTunes (apple.com/itunes) is a perfect tool to rip audio files from a CD into computer HD (MP3/AAC format). Besides copying all audio files in a CD, teacher can copy only specific files in a CD by ticking particular boxes. In addition, iTunes can compile selected audio files and burn them into CD (AIFF) or data disc (MP3). It is really a useful application for those who are not into sophisticated technique of audio ripping.

Audacity can also copy audio files into computer but it is complicated in terms of procedure. On the other hand, its feature rich makes Audacity powerful for editing audio files, such as, converting audio files into various codec (MP3, AAC, WMA, AIFF). He can also edit audio files, or tweaking the quality of audio files using Audacity. However, there will be to take a moderately long learning curve to be able to use this application well. On the bright side, there are plenty of tutorials available on internet which can be helpful to learn Audacity.

As to video files from DVDs, a universal format can be used to copy files which can be played in many multimedia gadgets. Since the video file of a DVD (VOB) takes a large space, there is a need to reduce its size and change it in a universal format (MP4). To do that, Handbrake (handbrake.fr) is free available application provided in multiple platforms (Windows, Mac, Linux). With Handbrake, users can convert video file from VOB into

MP4/mkv, which is smaller in size and still retains original quality. Interestingly, Handbrake can export VOB into MP4 (in different screen size resolutions) for various gadgets (iPod to tablet). With this ability, teachers are to distribute video files to his students who use different gadgets . Beyond distribution, the MP4 files enable teachers to edit the videos for specific needs using a video editing software; e.g. iMovie or WMM.

SIMPLE PHOTO MODIFICATION

Microsoft Paint and Paint.NET are already famous for free simple photo manipulation but Skitch (evernote.com/skitch) is absolutely useful for an even simpler photo editing task. After years of being a Mac exclusive app, Skitch is recently available for Windows and mobile gadgets (Android and iOS) after its acquisition by Evernote.

Skitch can be described as an application for PDF/photo annotation. Besides that, (for desktop version) Skitch can be used as screen capture with annotation feature, which is really useful if one wants to get an undownloadable photo from a website. The picture, and its annotation, can be exported into JPEG/PDF/PNG (desktop version) for further use. In case of mobile app, Skitch can annotate photo/PDF but it can only export the file into JPEG. To get PDF export feature, user has to make a purchase to Evernote.

Aside from annotating photo or PDF docs, ones can use Skitch as a tool to create a sketch. Whether using a mouse or stylus + table, Skitch will cover the users need. The ease of resizing Skitch window by stretching its window makes the job exporting a Skitch work a no-brainer skill. The learning curve in using Skitch is really short that even children will not get it wrong.

Since Skitch is available across platforms, its users can use the app on any device (desktop computer, tablet, smartphone) that uses major platforms (Macintosh, Windows, iOS, Android) without any hassle nor adjustment. In fact, the integration of Evernote into Skitch gave additional benefit to people who are already familiar with Evernote.

OTHER SOFTWARES

Another useful application to develop learning material is an application that turns a smartphone camera into a scanner. A teacher might come into a situation when he/she needs to make a softcopy of a document (hardcopy) but a paper scanner is nowhere to be found. Fortunately, a smartphone camera, and a small application, can act as a scanner and turn a photo into a PDF/JPEG file. CamScanner (Android and iOS) is a tiny application that utilizes

the camera of a smartphone to capture the image of a document (paper, poster, receipt, brochure, etc) and process the image into a PDF/JPEG file. After it has been processed, users may upload the scanned file into cloud or transfer it into computer (via Bluetooth). Next, the file can be used further to develop a learning material according to the teacher's wish.

CamScanner is available in two versions-Lite and Pro. The Lite version only allows users to use the application to capture image and share it via cloud (Google Drive or Dropbox) or bluetooth (desktop computer). However, the Lite version will never save file in phone/tablet harddisk. To enable direct saving inside a gadget, users have to purchase the Pro version. Based on personal experience, the Pro version is not really needed because it is cheaper to save the scanned file in the cloud or use bluetooth sharing. It is still better than using the "Camera to PDF" feature in Acrobat Reader application for tablet/smartphone.

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Khan Academy: <http://bit.ly/1cbWZj2>

SOFTWARE REFERENCES

Audio Editing & Mixing (Computer)

Audacity: www.sourceforge.audacity

iTunes: www.apple.com/itunes/download

Audio Editing & Mixing (Smartphone)

EZ Voice for iOS: <http://www.ikmultimedia.com/products/ezvoiceiphone/>

EZ Voice for Android: <http://www.ikmultimedia.com/products/ezvoiceandroid/>

iRig Recorder for Android: <http://www.ikmultimedia.com/products/irigrecorderandroid/>

iRig Recorder for iOS: <http://www.ikmultimedia.com/products/irigrecorder/>

Video Editing (Computer)

Any Video Converter: http://www.any-video-converter.com/products/for_video_free/

Handbrake: www.handbrake.fr

MPEG Streamclip: www.squared5.com

Video Recording & Editing (Smartphone)

YouTube Capture (iOS): <http://bit.ly/1n2WqDO>.

Photo Editing (Smartphone)

CamScanner for Android: <http://bit.ly/1nxrb0W>

CamScanner for iOS: <http://bit.ly/1mDrXVS>

Skitch for Android, iOS, Macintosh, and Windows: <https://evernote.com/skitch/>

Other Applications (Computer)

Downloadhelper: <http://bit.ly/1A65XPY>

JDownloader: <http://bit.ly/1isxAWC>

Google Apps for Android: <http://bit.ly/1EPSj0Y>

Google Apps for iOS: <http://bit.ly/1qO33qb>

RIGS FOR SMARTPHONE

Glif/Universal Glif: <http://www.studioneat.com/products/glif-universal>

JOBY Griptight : <http://joby.com/smartphones/griptight-mount>

iOgrapher (iOS Devices): <http://www.ioographer.com>